

MODERN SOURCES OF MARKET POWER OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS: CONCLUSIONS FOR ANTIMONOPOLY REGULATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888603>

Keywords: business activity, antimonopoly regulation, competition, monopolies, business law, business law

Currently, digital platforms are functioning in one way or another in many global and local markets. The scientific literature argues that in the modern digital age, they are the dominant form of doing business [Gawer, 2022]. The need for additional regulation of digital platforms is being actively discussed by researchers and antitrust authorities around the world [Baker, 2021; Ciriani & Lebourges, 2021]. The largest digital platforms are characterized by significant market power, but its manifestations and sources have not been fully studied [Flew, Gillett, 2021]. The focus of this study is precisely the second issue, in connection with which its purpose is to identify new potential sources of market power of digital platforms and provide appropriate recommendations for their accounting to regulatory authorities. The first part of the study provides a detailed theoretical analysis of the activities of digital platforms in the context of antimonopoly regulation issues. To do this, we first consider in detail the types of markets in which digital platforms operate [Shastitko, Markova, 2020], as well as the issue of defining their boundaries [Markova, 2022]. Then, based on a review of the literature, classical sources of market power of digital platforms are identified. These include, for example, the presence of a network effect on the market, brand loyalty, and increased returns on scale and investment [Bamberger, Lobel, 2017]. Based on the analysis of relevant theoretical literature, the hypothesis is put forward that big data and exclusive contracts should be attributed to potential sources of market power of digital platforms. It is argued that they can form new barriers to entry and strengthen existing ones. In the second part of the study, various methods of empirical analysis are used to confirm the hypothesis put forward. To identify the relationship between big data and the market power of digital platforms, the possibilities of their use in business processes, as well as real antitrust proceedings related to the use of big data by digital platforms, are analyzed. The assessment of the relationship between exclusive contracts and market power is based on the author's econometric model published in [Levakov, 2023].

The model identifies and evaluates the positive relationship between the share of exclusive contracts and the market share of the digital platform in the market. At the same time, it is customary in the scientific literature to associate a firm's market share with its market power [Rhoades, 1985]. Based on the analysis, it is argued that both big data and exclusive contracts can be considered as potential sources of market power for digital platforms, creating additional barriers to entry into the market. In the issue of regulating the use of big data, first of all, it is necessary to solve the issue of their classification. Quite often they are defined as public goods [Taylor, 2016], which creates obstacles to their effective regulation within the framework of antimonopoly legislation. As a possible solution to this problem, some categories of big data can be classified as club benefits [Radinsky, 2015]. The need for additional investments to conclude exclusive contracts has the most negative impact on new players in the market. Analyzing trends in exclusive contracts can also be a powerful tool for monitoring the state of the competitive environment in digital markets. Since they are concluded in advance, they allow you to predict the market shares of digital platforms in the future. Regarding the state of Russian antimonopoly legislation regarding the regulation of digital platforms, it can be concluded that it is currently insufficiently developed. The changes associated with the introduction of the term "network effect" at the legislative level can be positively assessed from this point of view. However, it is worth noting that in order to minimize the negative effect on competition, these changes had to be made much earlier

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